

Achieving Seamless IPv6 Connectivity for Next-Generation Two-Wheelers

Maria D. Garcia, Rafael M. Lopez

Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Texas Tech University, Lubbock, TX 79409, USA and Department of Computer Science, University of California, Irvine, CA 92697, USA

Abstract

Communications will be a must for two-wheel vehicles integrated into future smart mobility environments. Two-wheelers will be connected with vehicular networks and smart cities, and for this to happen it is necessary not only a base technological support, but also a proper communication middleware able to maintain reachable the bike or moped through the network. In this work, we present a communication node for two-wheelers supporting network mobility and including 3G and 802.11p communication technologies. The communication unit has been designed and prototyped, and it has been provided with an IPv6 communication stack with an enhanced mobility management. The operation of the unit has been assessed in real environments, presenting good performance results and thus offering a novel platform suitable for the next generation of telematics services embracing two-wheelers.

Indexed keywords: IPv6 mobility, two-wheelers, cooperative ITS, vehicular communications, performance evaluation

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1. Introduction

Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) imply a technological revolution applied to transport means. The objective of ITS is to achieve safer, more efficient and comfortable transport systems offering an enhanced experience to both drivers and passengers. Although initial contributions in the field of ITS were focused on autonomous systems installed in cars to improve safety by means of sensors, actuators and embedded computers, it has been in the last decade when advances in communication technologies have enabled the work on cooperative systems. Cooperative ITS (C-ITS) allow vehicles to communicate with other vehicles (V2V) and with the infrastructure (V2I), opening a broad set of novel services to appear. During the last years the research community has been actively developing communication mechanisms

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especially designed to satisfy the challenges posed by cooperative ITS services. However, the effort in this line focused on the two-wheelers area is limited, considering that there are

15 European recommendations for further research [1]. Special considerations, such as power source, vehicle dynamics, communication and positioning capabilities, user interfaces, or hardware integration within the vehicle, should be considered in communication units to be developed for bikes, mopeds and motorbikes. Once covered, a hardware/software platform like this could be of great use to include 20 these means of transport in the future vehicular networks.

For C-ITS to happen, a network that interconnects all the different elements of the road is necessary. In this field, different standardization bodies have defined its own reference communication architecture, as it is simplified in Fig. 1.

IEEE have bet for Wireless Access in Vehicular Environments (WAVE), whose

25 most relevant technology in the last years has been 802.11p, also called *Vehicular WiFi*, which provides the physical and access layers of the stack. ETSI and ISO propose an architecture with an exchangeable access technology, and propose different routing protocols. What is remarkable in these three proposals is the presence of the IPv6 protocol, although it has received a marginal interest

30 and it is mainly considered by these organizations as a complementary network protocol mainly for infotainment applications. However, we understand IPv6 as an essential piece of a vehicular communication stack to embed vehicular networks in the Future Internet.

In IPv6-based vehicular networks, the provision of network mobility mech-

35 anisms that make survive communication sessions upon the change of IP addressing has been considered using *Mobile IP* technologies. The research line

Figure 1: Different reference architectures for vehicular networks

followed in our previous work [2] proposes the use of the *Network Mobility Basic Support* (NEMO) protocol [3] defined by the IETF. Despite NEMO was designed for common IP access networks, we have successfully demonstrated its

40 applicability in IP-based vehicular scenarios, as it enables the mobility of entire networks, making it perfect for vehicles, where an internal network to connect car and user devices is highly beneficial. The challenge now is to port this architecture to a constrained unit for two-wheelers, in order they can access the vehicular

network in the same way to also enable IoT communication patterns ⁴⁵ and integration in new Smart City environments.

The work described in this paper exploits this research gap, with the aim of providing a communication unit able to access vehicular IPv6 networks in two-wheel vehicular environments. For this, the proposal raises from the synergy between current ITS standards (ISO/ETSI), Internet protocols (IETF)

⁵⁰ and IEEE technologies. The solution is an embedded communication unit for two-wheel vehicles integrating IEEE 802.11p and 3G wireless technologies in a small-factor computer, and running a communication middleware based on mobile IPv6 with NEMO support. Apart from the design, the work is especially focused on the prototype of the platform and real network performance tests, ⁵⁵ which provides an added value to the contribution.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 places this work in the research literature. Section 3 describes the general scenario of the ITS communication system. Section 4 describes the design and development of the new communication unit for two-wheelers, while Section 5 includes the experimental evaluation ⁶⁰ of this system.

Section 6 analyses the results and discusses future directions.

Finally, Section 7 concludes the paper.

2. State of the Art

A proper scientific knowledge supporting the application of C-ITS technologies in two-wheelers is limited in the literature, and nonexistent when dealing

⁶⁵ with network mobility in this field, as far as the authors know. The authors in [4] have recently discussed the importance of communications for enhancing safety and efficiency of VRU and, particularly, the protection of two-wheelers. Several works in the literature already deal with road safety regarding pedestrians, which are the ones that barely cite two-wheelers in the area of traffic safety.

⁷⁰ In [5] a review of systems to protect pedestrians reveals that until 2007 communications were rarely used to create cooperative systems, and vision, thermal, radar or laser sensors were used to avoid vehicle collisions with VRU. The paper in [6] follows the same approach, although the authors emphasise the greater complexity on tracking VRU in contrast with tracking a common vehicle. The

⁷⁵ proliferation of lower-delay cellular connections and the wide usage of WiFi contributed to the appearance of cooperative solutions around 2010. In [7] the base idea of exchanging localisation data among pedestrian mobile phones and car on-board devices is presented. Here a 3G link is mainly used, although it is also discussed the establishment of a WiFi connection between both terminals

⁸⁰ to reduce communication delay. A similar system is presented in [8] and [9], although they analyse in more detail the implications of the communication technology used. The authors in [10] review a communication technology in the 700 MHz for pedestrian to vehicle communication, which is far from current

USA and EU trend of working in the microwave band. The solution presented

⁸⁵ in this paper focuses on the use of vehicular WiFi technology in the 5 GHz band for short-range vehicular communications, whose potential for communications between cars and VRU is discussed in [11], and cellular networks for ubiquitous access to Internet when 802.11p is not available.

In [12, 13] there is a work where telematics are integrated in bicycles, by

⁹⁰ means of a ZigBee-based prototype to enable platooning. The proposal is not based on current C-ITS architecture standards, but it includes an interesting equipment that has been embedded in the bike with a tactile interface. The integration of hardware in the two-wheeler section is also discussed in [14], although the maturity of communication technologies did not allowed the solution

⁹⁵ to be provided with current cooperative advantages in the ITS sector. The work analyses the potential of wearable devices for bikes and mopeds, which is one of the next steps in our research work. This line is exploited in [15], presenting a system that uses a new belt designed as user interface with a navigation system provided by a mobile phone. No particular attention is paid to communications,

¹⁰⁰ and a common 3G link is used to access Google Maps information. The authors in [16] present a connected motorbike provided with a communication unit that supports vehicular WiFi (5 GHz). The issue found in this work is the lack of a protocol stack supporting standardised high-level protocols in the ITS sector and, among them, the ones allowing Internet connection. The work in [17, 18]

¹⁰⁵ is focused on light two-wheel vehicles, presenting a safety system to warn cyclist about the presence of other vehicles through a visual interface embedded in the helmet. However, as a difference with the present contribution, it is based exclusively on a 3G/4G connection through the mobile phone for the case of the bike.

¹¹⁰ The work in [19] presents a system that also uses a mobile phone for a similar purpose, although the novelty in this case is found in the way that regular WiFi is used. Beacon messages are used to directly embed information about a safety service, thus avoiding the association. A drawback of this proposal is its narrow application perspective and the need of using this especial communi-

¹¹⁵ cation mode of WiFi. A work including standardised vehicular communication protocols is described in [20], where motorbikes are equipped with a unit using

an ETSI-compliant communication stack, while bikes use a especial bluetooth low-consumption device. Although this work share with the present contribution the idea of connecting two-wheelers to the vehicular network, it is focused

¹²⁰ on concrete vehicular protocols, setting IPv6 aside, and thus not addressing network mobility issues for continuous Internet connectivity.

As can be seen in the summary of related works included in Table 1, several contributions are found in the pedestrian-to-vehicle communication domain, and this is even a very recent research field. The predominant communication

¹²⁵ technology is cellular, through the use of mobile phones, and thus not dealing with the integration of specific hardware (referred as *HW int.* in Table 1) in the vehicle or in the form of new wearable devices. Additionally, works especially tackling two-wheelers connectivity present protocol stacks that do not consider the interconnection of these transportation means with the rest of the Internet.

¹³⁰ Standardised communication architectures (referred as *Std. arch.* in Table 1) are rarely used and none of the related works includes network mobility. We think that IPv6 is the key piece of smart cities and, for sure, of Future Internet architectures and, for this reason, we present a communication unit able to integrate two-wheelers in current IPv6 vehicular networks by supporting continuous ¹³⁵ Internet connectivity through mobile IPv6 technologies.

3. Overall System Architecture

The overall architecture and main subsystems of the proposal are illustrated in Fig. 2. Vehicles are provided with a mobile router and other nodes (such as a proper visual interface unit) connected with it through an in-vehicle network.

¹⁴⁰ The communication stack is based on IPv6, as it has been successfully tested by us in [2]. This stack follows the ISO/ETSI reference architecture specifications [21, 22]. The bike, electrical bike or light moped is provided with this communication node supporting vehicular WiFi and 3G. This has been prototyped as an embedded on-board device, with battery power supply, GPS

¹⁴⁵ and the proper communication transceivers. Basic applications can run on this

Table 1: Most related works in cooperative ITS for two-wheelers in the areas of pedestrian

(*Ped*) / bike (*Bike*) / motorbike (*Mot*) to vehicle communications

		Area				
[7]		Ped	3G/WiFi	5	5	5
[8]		Ped	3G/WiFi	5	5	5
[9]		Bik	3G/WiFi	5	5	5
[10]		Ped	700 MHz	5	5	5
[12]		Bik	ZigBee	5	5	3
[15]		Bik	3G	5	5	5
[16]		Mot	802.11p	5	5	3
		Bike	3G/4G	3	5	3
[19]			WiFi	5	5	5
[20]		Mot		3	5	5

unit, or in a mobile device connected with it. Both vehicle and two-wheeler mobile routers can use the specific ITS network to directly communicate in adhoc mode, as used in [23], or use this medium to reach Internet through an

802.11p access router. Alternatively, an Internet access is possible using the 3G

¹⁵⁰ transceiver (the one included in the car mobile router is omitted for the sake of clarity in Fig. 2). Network mobility through NEMO allows handovers between both technologies.

The communication stack of the new embedded unit for two-wheelers has been ported from the one used in the car mobile router. Its main design blocks

¹⁵⁵ are depicted in Fig. 3. IPv6 connectivity is supported by the set of elements included within the networking and transport layer of the unit. NEMO [3] is in charge of maintaining IPv6 reachability. Regarding security,

the mobile router is equipped with the needed elements to secure mobility-related traffic by means of Internet Protocol Security (IPsec) [24]. This security service is not taken into
 160 consideration for the performance evaluations carried out in this work, given its small influence in the overall network performance, as it is discussed in our

Figure 2: Overall scenario of the communication system

prior work [2].

The mobility service of the mobile router is implemented by an application running in background mode (daemon). Another instance of this software is
 165 also required in the home network, which plays the role of Home Agent in the mobile IPv6 terminology. NEMO functionality allows an in-vehicle network to be globally connected with Internet. For this to be done, the mobile network maintains IPv6 addressing through changes in the final point of attachment or network access. The tasks to be covered by NEMO are shared between the
 170 mobile router, within the mobile network, and the home agent, which is setup within a known administrative domain. The home agent is notified of changes in the access network used by the mobile router to reach the Internet and, this way, ongoing data flows survive through a tunnel maintained between the

Figure 3: Design of the mobile router with extended IPv6 mobility support

two nodes. This task is performed transparently to the nodes connected in the
 175 in-vehicle network and the remote communication peers. When ported to the two-wheeler area, IPv6-
 powered wearable and embedded devices on the bike or moped maintain addressing during itinerancy.
 The basic operation of NEMO is summarised next. The mobile router always has a long-term IP address
 called *Home Address* (HoA), the one that it
 180 uses when it is connected to the home network. When the unit enters a different network domain, a new
 IP address is generated, this one called *Care-of-address* (CoA). This CoA is only used to reach the home agent.
 When connected outside the home network, the mobile router forwards all the traffic from in-vehicle devices
 to the home agent, and this one performs the same action in the opposite
 185 direction when a corresponding node (usually in the Internet) wants to communicate with an in-vehicle
 device. Hence, the home agent needs to associate each HoA with at least one CoA. For this reason, the mobile
 router has to notify the home agent about this new CoA. These notifications are performed using the *Binding
 Update* (BU) and *Binding Acknowledgement* (BA) messages defined in
 190 the NEMO protocol. Thanks to these signaling messages, a binding cache is kept up-to-date in the home
 agent, where each HoA is associated with one or more CoAs.
 Additionally, when the mobile router maintains more than one interface simultaneously up (3G and 802.11p
 in our case) and has multiple paths to the
 195 Internet, it is said to be *multihomed*. With the aim of supporting multihoming, the IETF developed the
 MCoA extension for NEMO [25], which is included in our unit, as Fig. 3 shows. This technology allows us to
 perform faster handovers, maintaining initial and target communication flows up during the transition.
 However, in order to better decide the most suitable network at every single

location, we have also included modules from the IEEE 802.21 standard, as it was initially presented in [26].

4. Embedded Hardware Platform

A new communication unit has been created for the case of two-wheel vehicles, including necessary communication technologies and providing a proper software host. The unit was initially presented in [27], considering a basic communication middleware for a constrained safety application, and presenting an initial prototype. The platform has been now improved to support IPv6 network mobility to act as mobile router, which allows the execution of final applications in mobile devices connected with the unit. Moreover, the prototype has been assembled in its final form, being totally operational, as it is demonstrated in Section 5.

4.1. General Architecture of the Unit

The general architecture of the unit is depicted in Fig. 4. The microprocessor unit (MPU) board contains the base platform, with the CPU, USB, and communication modules supporting Ethernet, UMTS (3G), vehicular WiFi, GPS and regular WiFi, which is mainly used to connect with mobile devices installed

Figure 4: Hardware design of the communication unit

on the two-wheeler or carried by the user(s). These modules are connected with an appropriate antenna. The main board is powered by a Lithium battery, given that the two-wheel vehicle could not include a power supply (e.g. bikes).

A basic human-machine interface (HMI) is given by an extra board including LEDs and a Buzzer, which can be used to execute basic warning services or for testing purposes.

4.2. Prototype

A reference prototype of the unit design has been implemented and installed ²²⁵ in both a bike and a moped. Fig. 5 shows the main parts of the hardware. An overall view of the platform is included in Fig. 5a, where both the main unit (bottom in black) and the HMI board (upper in blue) are mounted on an electric moped. Fig. 5b shows the hardware included in the main unit, which includes the functional modules of the MPU board described above. The unit is

²³⁰ based on the Laguna LGN-20 platform from Commsignia. The communication board is visible on the top, from where different cables are connected to the 802.11p, regular WiFi (802.11n), GPS and 3G antennas. This system mounts an ARM11 300MHz SoC processor, 16 MB of flash memory and 8 GB of internal storage, and 256 MB of RAM. The USB interface is used to connect with the

(a) Unit mounted on a moped

(b) MPU board

(c) Lithium battery

(d) HMI board

Figure 5: Prototype of the communication unit for two-wheeled vehicles

²³⁵ HMI board. The power supply used is a 15 volts and 3500 mA lithium battery showed in Fig. 5c, which is able to maintain the unit up more than six hours in the operation modes used in the tests presented in Section 5. The 802.11p antenna used is a 5.9 Ghz Taoglas Limited DCP.5900.12.4.A.02 (6 dBi), which has been affixed to the inner part of the unit enclosure, and it is visible on

²⁴⁰ the upper right corner in Fig. 5b. No 802.11n antennas have been used for the moment, and the cables are maintained in a foam piece, but communication with near devices has been possible without them. The 3G antenna is a common stick used for WiFi, and it is connected on the lower left corner of the unit.

The HMI board is a new design, including a set of LEDs and a buzzer. The
245 prototype is showed in Fig. 5d. One of the LEDs is used to inform about the whole unit status, while the
others and the buzzer (clearly visible in black) are left for application purposes, such as the safety service for
two-wheelers described in [27]. The USB connector is used to attach the circuit to the main board, as can be
seen in Fig. 5a. The GPS antenna has been finally installed
250 in the same enclosure used for the HMI in order to avoid interferences with the main unit electronics and
improve the signal reception. This antenna is a PCTEL WS3917, which has worked correctly in the tests.

4.3. Communication Middleware

The communication stack used has been ported from our previous research [2]
255 to the new unit. A cross compiler has been used to adapt a communication stack initially created in the
ITSSv6 project¹ and port it to the ARM-based communication unit. The base communication middleware has
been modified to support MCoA and 802.21, as said above, but a key software module used is *mip6d*, which
is the mobility daemon in charge of implementing the base NEMO proto²⁶⁰ col. The IEEE 802.21 support
comes from the ODTONE² open source software. This is a reference IEEE 802.21 implementation including
basic functionalities, which is being adapted to our needs. At the moment, the operation of the 802.21
functionality is under tests, so it was disabled for the tests carried out in this work.
265 Apart from the regular TCP/IP(v6) communication support, the unit is provided with a standard messaging
scheme using CAM packets standardized by ETSI, which are coded in DER ASN.1 as defined in [28]. By using
these messages as explained in [27], the unit is capable of sending status information to the surrounding
vehicles in a direct V2V fashion, by encapsulating CAM
270 information into UDP datagrams sent to the *all nodes* ff02::1 address and using a link-local IPv6 address.

Due to the telecomm operator used does not provide IPv6 connectivity at
the moment in Spain, a VPN tunnel over IPv4 is used to send IPv6 traffic over the 3G link. The software used
for this is OpenVPN³.

5. Experimental Evaluation

The communication unit for two-wheelers has been tested in two different scenarios to assess its performance
in real driving settings. The first one is focused on analysing communications in a one-hop basis, testing the
802.11p link in a direct line of sight environment. The second scenario has been mounted
280 to completely test network mobility by using both 802.11p and 3G communica-
tions.

1
2
3

5.1. Short Range Communication Tests

5.1.1. Testbed

The first testing scenario was set in the surroundings of the University Centre of Defence at the Spanish Air Force Academy. The deployment was quite simple, since in this case we were interested in testing the basic communication capabilities of the unit with another communication node. For the sake of simplicity we preferred to move a second mobile router in a car, and maintain static the two-wheeler node, since this one has a battery and it is not necessary an external power supply. Fig. 6a shows the open road where the tests were performed, in which there is direct line of sight between the two-wheeler unit and the car mobile router. The new embedded node was detached from the moped and placed in a box on the sidewalk, next to the road and elevated 10 cm, as can be seen in Fig. 6b. The HMI board (blue box) was connected just to check the correct operation of the unit through one of the LEDs, while the GPS antenna was necessary to geo-localise the unit. The box was placed at the middle of the road stretch showed in Fig. 6a. The car used for the tests is showed in Fig. 6c, while the mobile router is showed in Fig. 6d. This mobile router is a

Figure 6: First scenario for testing one-hop communications using 802.11p

Laguna LGN-20 from Commsignia, running a communication stack equivalent to the one included in the two-wheeler node. The antenna used is a combined omnidirectional 3G/11p/GPS 7dBi, which was attached on the vehicle roof with a magnetic base. The tests have been carried out with three different protocols:

- ICMPv6, to check the delay of the communication link. A continuous

305 check of the link using the *ping6* tool at a rate of 1 Hz and with a payload of 56 bytes has been performed.

- UDP, to study packet losses. It has been chosen a transmission rate of 1 Mbps, sending 1230 bytes of data in each datagram. The *iperf* tool⁴ is used to generate this UDP traffic.

310 • TCP, to study the maximum achievable throughput. The *iperf* tool has

Table 2: Configuration parameters used by software modules in the short range communication

tests

Node		Parameter	Value
er node	ping6	Request rate	1 Hz
er node	ping6	Payload	56 B
Mobile router	ping6	Request rate	1 Hz
Mobile router	ping6	Payload	56 B
er node	iperf	ate	
er node	iperf	UDP payload	1230 B
Mobile router	iperf	ate	
Mobile router	iperf	UDP payload	1230 B
er node	iperf	ate	
Mobile router	iperf	ate	

been used for this again.

Table 2 summarizes the main configuration parameters out of default settings. Each transmission type was used to pass six times with the car near the two-wheeler node, and different tests were carried out to check the car to two-

315 wheeler transmission direction, and the two-wheeler to car one. Each record of the test was geo-located by marking it with the GPS position. This way the results obtained have been averaged in a 10 meter basis, computing the distance from the car to the two-wheeler node.

5.1.2. Results

320 The delay results obtained in the tests are showed in Fig. 7, presenting delay results for both the two-wheeler to car and car to two-wheeler traffic directions. As can be seen, a good performance is obtained within a communication range of near 600 meters. Out of this stretch the communication path is broken and

⁴ <https://iperf.fr>

ICMP reply packets are not received. The round-trip time value obtained in ³²⁵ most of the stretch is between 1.5 and 2 ms. Delay peaks are obtained at the edges of the road stretch just before the communication is broken. As can be seen in the plots, the results gathered in both communication directions are equivalent, given that the *ping6* generates *Echo Request* packets that reach the destination and then *Echo Reply* messages come back; hence, both uplink and ³³⁰ downlink data links are tested in the two cases.

The study of the packet delivery ratio (PDR), which is measured in percentage of packets that successfully reach the destination, is showed in Fig. 8. As expected, a similar communication range is obtained here, and good PDR results are obtained within near 600 meters of the road stretch. However, it can ³³⁵ be observed that the two-wheeler to car case performs better. This is due to the better reception sensibility of the antenna used in the car unit.

TCP results are plotted in the two graphs included in Fig. 9. The first noticeable difference with the previous tests is the communication range decrease.

This is attributed to the features of the communication protocol used, since

³⁴⁰ TCP needs a successful connection establishment stage prior to start the transmission. After that, the transmission rate is adapted according to the detected performance of the link. This adaptation is performed on the assumption that losses are caused by congestion, which reveal the problem of using TCP in highdemanding throughput scenarios. Again, it is observed that in the two-wheeler ³⁴⁵ to car case, the link performs in a steadier way. In any case, in both types of transmission, the maximum throughput obtained reaches 4 Mbps, which is a good value.

5.2. Network Mobility Tests

5.2.1. Testbed

³⁵⁰ The testbed depicted in Fig. 10 has been deployed in the Campus of the University of Murcia (UMU) to test network mobility capabilities of the twowheeler communication node. The diagram shows the two available communication routes: the one supported by means of an 802.11p access, and the one provided by using the 3G operator's infrastructure. The addressing scheme is ³⁵⁵ also showed in the diagram. As can be noted, all IPv6 addresses belong to a

Figure 7: Averaged delay results using one-hop communication and 802.11p

special testing purpose range. Apart from the nodes used in the previous scenario, an additional node supporting 802.11p is used as access router, to reach the rest of the infrastructure network, and the home agent has been deployed to enable NEMO operation. The OpenVPN tunnel is used to support IPv6 over

(b) Car to two-wheeler

Figure 8: Averaged packet delivery results using one-hop communication and 802.11p

360 the cellular network, as indicated in Section 4.

Fig. 11 shows the new equipment used in this testbed. The access router is a Laguna LGN-20 by Commsignia, and it uses the communication stack of the mobile router of the previous scenario. This unit is connected with a 12 dBi

(a) Two-wheeler to car

(b) Car to two-wheeler

Figure 9: Averaged throughput results using one-hop communication and 802.11p

stick antenna for 802.11p communications, which has been placed in a window of the Faculty of Computer Engineering. The home agent is a small-factor VIA PC with 476 MB of main memory and processor of 532 Mhz, and using the communication stack included in the mobile router of the previous scenario.

Figure 10: Second scenario using network mobility and 3G/802.11p communications

This node is located in a different laboratory of the building, but it is directly wired with the access router through a switch. Moreover, an electric vehicle of

the UMU fleet is used to mount the two-wheeler communication node, as can be seen in Fig. 11b. A list of the most important configuration parameters used in several components of the testbed is provided in Table 3. Router Advertisement messages are used to detect new access routers. The transmission period of these packets has been reduced in the 802.11p interface with the aim of minimizing the time spent to detect the presence of an access router. The maximum lifetime of communication paths with the home agent is included in the last row of the table. This indicates the maximum time a care of address is maintained associated with a home address for a communication node, after the last binding update is received. The values of these parameters have been adjusted from the experience gained by the authors in previous deployments of IPv6 networks in highways [29].

The tests consist of a repeated trial in which a vehicle moves within the Espinardo Campus at the University of Murcia (see Fig. 12). The vehicle follows a traced path where the 3G coverage is always present, but the 802.11p coverage

Figure 11: Equipment used in the second testbed

Table 3: Configuration parameters used by software modules in the mobility scenario

Node		Parameter	Value
Access Router	radvd	RA rate (3G)	3-4 s
Access Router	radvd	RA rate (802.11p)	0.5-1 s
Mobile Router	mip6d	lifetime	12 s
er node	ping6	Request rate	1 Hz
er node	ping6	Payload	56 B
Home Agent	iperf	UDP trans. rate	pps

Home Agent	iperf	UDP payload	1230 B
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is limited to a part of the circuit, which corresponds to the place where the access router has been installed. This can be seen in the image with a coverage plot on the map. In every trial, the vehicle performs a whole lap to the circuit, using both technologies at different times. As a result, (at least) two handover processes are expected in every trial, one from 3G to 802.11p and another one from 802.11p to 3G. All trials have been performed trying to maintain the same speed of 30 Km/h, since in our previous work [2] we observed that this is the most interesting and realistic case.

The tests have been performed using the next protocols and parameters (as

Figure 12: Path of the tests with the 802.11p signal level

included in Table 3):

- ICMPv6, to check the delay of the communication link. A continuous check of the link using the *ping6* tool at a rate of 1 Hz and with a payload of 56 bytes has been performed from the two-wheeler unit to the home agent, in order to assess the delay time when crossing the mobility tunnel.

- UDP, to study the packet losses. It has been chosen the transmission rates 100 Kbps and 300 Kbps, sending 1230 bytes of data in each datagram. The *iperf* tool is used to generate this UDP traffic from the HA to the two-wheeler node.

5.2.2. Results

The results obtained in one of the delay tests carried out are depicted in

Fig. 13. As can be seen, the delay obtained clearly marks the areas where 802.11p and 3G are used. There are only some packet losses during the test,

Figure 13: Delay tests using network mobility

but the jitter of the communication channel is evident because of the mobility conditions. The handover to the 802.11p technology is initiated when a Router

⁴¹⁰ Advertisement message is received from the access router, however, thanks to the MCoA technology, only when the path is ready the traffic start to be routed through this new link towards the home agent. Delay values obtained when using the cellular network are in the baseline of 100 ms, while values around 5 ms are obtained when the handover to the access router is performed.

⁴¹⁵ The values obtained during the three trials performed with ICMP traffic are summarised in Table 4. The RTT values obtained when using 802.11p are clearly lower. We have detected an improvement in the cellular network in the last years, according to our previous work in [2]. This is attributed to the High Speed Packet Access (HSPA) improvements of the network. 802.11p

⁴²⁰ values are also better, comparing with our previous results, which is due to the improvement of the communication transceiver used in both the two-wheeler node and the access router. The jitter observed in Fig. 13 is now reflected in

Table 4 by 95% confidence intervals obtained, which are higher in the 3G case.

Table 4: Results obtained in delay tests using network mobility

	1				
1	3G	128	121.45 ms	6.14 ms	
					15

1	11p	83	5.40 ms		
2	3G	129	112.03 ms	3.83 ms	1
2	11p	82	8.04 ms	1.24 ms	
3	3G	143	140.26 ms	8.28 ms	3
3	11p	78	5.05 ms	0.87 ms	

It is important to consider that the 3G network is a shared infrastructure whose capacity depends on the connected users, while the 802.11p deployment is only operated by us. Regarding packet losses, a bus blocked the line of sight with the access router for a while in the first test, causing a connectivity gap and, hence, several consecutive packet losses.

Fig. 14 shows the PDR values in one of the tests carried out with a transmission rate of 100 Kbps. The availability of the 802.11p-powered access router is marked with a dotted line indicating the RSS perception from the mobile router (two-wheeler node) point of view. Several losses are detected in the handover from 802.11p to 3G, due to the degradation of the 802.11p channel. Nevertheless, the overall performance of the network is good, with a baseline of 100% of packet deliveries.

In order to completely assess the performance of the solution in terms of packet losses, a summary of the results obtained in six trials is included in Table 5. The results reveal that the increase of transmission rate does not impact on the performance, since the channel is only used by one terminal and the maximum bandwidth of 802.11p is still far from these values. More important is checking that the PDR statistics are quite good, even though the 802.11p communication path could be chosen without detecting a good enough signal level from the access router.

Fig. 15 maps in a satellite photo the usage of the 802.11p path in light blue

Figure 14: Packet losses using network mobility at 100 Kbps

Table 5: Results obtained in packet delivery tests using network mobility

1	100 Kbps	239	94.80%	±1.17%
2	100 Kbps	191	98.31%	±0.49%
3	100 Kbps	198	95.37%	±1.00%
4	300 Kbps	177	97.22%	±0.84%
5	300 Kbps	197	95.57%	±0.98%
6	300 Kbps	201	95.93%	±0.97%

⁴⁴⁵ (from 100 m to 500 m marks) and the usage of the 3G path in red (from 500 m to 100 m marks), after checking that this operation is common in all the tests. The handover to 802.11p is performed in the first roundabout, and this communication path is maintained through the whole road stretch on the main street along 400 meters. Since the antenna of the access router is affixed to
⁴⁵⁰ a window of the building just in front of the point marked with 300 m, the coverage angle is limited to 180 degrees, and the signal level is highly dependent

Figure 15: Connectivity and handovers performed over the vehicle path

on the lack of line of sight due to the near buildings showed in the photo. Comparing with the signal level plotted in Fig. 12, it can be checked that as soon as there is 802.11p coverage and a Router Advertisement message is received,⁴⁵⁵ the communication path through the access router is chosen.

6. Discussion and Future Aspects

The results obtained indicate a good performance of the 802.11p communication link. The delay and PDR results assure a good operation of the network for safety services requiring direct V2V communications. Moreover, the good

⁴⁶⁰ throughput of the link enables the cellular network offload for services such as video transmission or file downloading, always when a near roadside unit is available. Nevertheless, it must be considered that the expected performance when driving near multiple vehicles using 802.11p resources would be impacted by the number of units in the surroundings and their transmission needs.

⁴⁶⁵ The mobility results indicate a good operation of the unit in a real network mobility environment, presenting the communication unit for two-wheelers as a potential platform for infrastructure-based services and IoT connectivity patterns. RTT values of 2 ms and 5 ms has been measured in V2V and network

mobility tests, respectively; and low packet losses are detected in communication

⁴⁷⁰ ranges of 400 m. Moreover, it is important to note that the unit and on-board nodes connected with it are continuously reachable by their IPv6 address. This is essential in remote monitoring and automation tasks for future transportation, which will be highly coupled with Smart City solutions for emission control, mobility assistance or parking support, among others.

⁴⁷⁵ As compared with the related works discussed at the beginning, and summarized in Table 1, the system presented in this paper embraces the area of two-wheelers, including bikes, mopeds and motorbikes, by using

a communication stack based on standards coming from ISO/ETSI C-ITS communication architectures and IETF protocols. The solution in [16] includes a partial im-

480 plementation of the WAVE stack, but this does not assure the openness of the system in the Internet or its interconnection with other networked systems. Although the prototype includes 3G/4G and vehicular WiFi, the system is prepared to be extended with other communication technologies to enable other “in-vehicle” devices, or additional means to reach the Internet or other vehicles.

485 The proposal includes an embedded mobile router to be mounted on the vehicle, and a future direction will be designing wearable IPv6 devices to provide safety and traffic efficiency services, such as smart helmets or vests including warning notifications to near vehicles. Moreover, the proposal is the only one integrating network mobility in the two-wheeler segment, as far as the authors know. This

490 is of particular importance for the next urban mobility scenarios to come, where all vehicles should be connected in smart scenarios.

This work opens a promising research line in the area of vehicular communications for two-wheelers. Thanks to the performance analysis carried out, we have identified a potential improvement in the mobility, by including an on-

495 going implementation of 802.21 modules that will allow the unit to better decide the communication path to choose depending on measurements from the same unit, such as the signal strength, and details about the surrounding networks received from a especial server. It is expected that this solves the problem of using a communication path with a poor signal strength, which is something

500 we have detected at the edges of the road stretch where the 802.11p channel is used, for instance.

Security issues will be further analysed in our future work, complementing our prior work in [2]. Our current approach is based on session-based security using IPsec, however, there are current standardization lines betting on certifi-

505 cates. Privacy management is another hot topic in a data gathering scenario such as the vehicular one; hence, the application of pseudonyms is another line to be considered in the future.

Our next steps will also consider out base communication platform to connect all means of transport with a Smart City infrastructure through the use of

510 IoT protocols. Message Queue Telemetry Transport (MQTT) or Constrained Application Protocol (CoAP) are identified as good candidates to be used on the top of our stack, given that they are prepared to be used over IP networks while saving power resources, which could be interesting for the two-wheeler communication node. This will allow us to gather data from the whole trans-

515 portation network, opening a new frame of potential services involving bicycles in multimodal schemes, integral vehicle sharing mechanisms, green tracks, or pollution monitoring and mitigation.

7. Conclusion

This paper describes the design and implementation of a communication
520 node for two-wheelers, which supports both cellular and short-range communications, and includes a communication stack capable of maintaining IPv6 connectivity and addressing by using network mobility. The design of the unit guides the implementation of a system adapted to bikes or mopeds (and, in general, small-factor vehicles), which satisfies the networking needs of many 525 services envisaged in cooperative ITS scenarios.

A prototype of the unit has been used in real tests performed under real traffic conditions, which demonstrate the stability of the unit and show good figures of merit of the solution. The delay and packet losses of the system have been evaluated in both direct V2V and infrastructure-based communications

⁵³⁰ by using network mobility, in order to bound the expected performance for as many potential services as possible.

The on-board node presented in this paper is the first solution in the literature providing network mobility in the two-wheel segment, as far as the authors know. It follows standards in the cooperative ITS sector, exploiting the synergy

⁵³⁵ between ISO/ETSI standards for ITS and IETF protocols. This enables the interoperation with the Internet and other network infrastructures. The proposal leaves the door open for new research lines in the areas of communication technologies for two-wheelers, human-machine interface for these vehicles, services for improving safety and mobility in this area, integration with smart cities, or ⁵⁴⁰ inclusion of IoT protocols for remote monitoring and control, among others.

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